

A SYSTEMATIC MODEL OF THE FORMATION OF ACCULTURATIVE SKILLS IN STUDENTS IN THE TEACHING OF HISTORY

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Annotation: As a result of the restoration of historical values, the growing process of national identity of peoples, important positive changes are taking place in the way of thinking. These changes taking place in our lives are absorbed into people's hearts and minds, and they are cultivating a sense of confidence in the future, a sense of freedom and liberty. The new development strategy paves the way for us to enjoy our rich cultural and spiritual heritage, the springs of spirituality created by our great ancestors. Inculcating the process of education based on such historical values to students and developing acculturative skills based on their pedagogical activity remains one of the priority tasks.

Key words and phrases: science, history, value, society, innovation, educational efficiency, systematic model, spiritual heritage.

Another problem in the history education of general secondary education is explained by the fact that a narrow and shallow approach is used in instilling knowledge about historical events. Such an approach has a negative effect on the students' historical imagination and they understand it as a story consisting of high-minded statements about historical heroes. Therefore, scientific and pedagogical thinking is always carried out on the issue of making history a reality. This issue has become important for education in recent years. After all, historical knowledge is built on an objective basis, and when it acquires a positive content, the nation first deeply understands its historical roots, by analyzing the processes that happened in the past, drawing the necessary conclusions from them, and having a deeper understanding of the reasons and factors that created the real reality, it is based on the fact that it affects the development of the national historical memory [1].

So, in teaching history:

- 1) necessary to create a correct image of the past;
- 2) facilitates understanding of the past;
- 3) helps to strengthen knowledge;
- 4) increases his interest in being similar to historical heroes and taking an example from them. This complex of educational tasks is one of the most important tasks of educating the growing young generation in the spirit of patriotism and increasing interest in the profession. Historical education is one of the important factors of formation of high idealism in students, correct approach to history, working in an active life position, strengthening of knowledge and formation of organization [2].

Such a responsible task set before the education system by the society has a great impact on the development of the science of pedagogy. It is recognized that one of the directions of such development is active education. By active education, we understand the system of factors that ensure the conscious and active participation, independence and

creative abilities of students, who are considered the main object and subject of the educational process. In any activity, as well as in educational activities, activity does not appear by itself, but as the Polish scientist Okon noted, "The basis of student activity is the realization of the importance and necessity of the educational material for the present and the future, the desire to master it perfectly, interest, and the intellectual satisfaction of finding a solution to the educational problem." It is known that the activity of such a person arises by awakening certain needs. One of the most urgent problems is to activate students' educational activities, to develop independence and creativity in them. Because the conscious activity, independence and creativity of students characterizes the quality of the result of their educational activity" [3]. Historical memory is important as an important factor in the formation of the above qualities in students.

From these comments, it can be understood that deep knowledge of one's own past, the path traveled by ancestors, and drawing correct conclusions from the history of other nations, their achievements and mistakes are interpreted as one of the factors that lead to the development of each nation.

Many factors of activation are noted in the theory and practice of pedagogy. In our opinion, one of such important factors is updating the educational material.

World experience shows that one of the reasons for the rapid development of some countries is that they realized and correctly implemented the organization of national education. Undoubtedly, Uzbekistan has a similar well-thought-out education system. However, the main content of its implementation was the correct establishment of all areas of education, first of all, history education, including the effective use of the task of developing historical ideals in the pedagogical process, and the expansion of students' historical thinking through historical knowledge.

The goal of each lesson is to first of all form the conclusions of the students about the historical facts and awaken their personal opinion. When evaluating each student, it is necessary to look at the extent to which the subject of the lesson is proven, based on evidence, based on historical sources. The famous pedagogue V.A. Sukhomlinsky emphasizes the organic interaction and interdependence between different fields and forms of education, and believes that the most important thing in this process is the problem of harmonizing pedagogical influences.

Under the leadership of Professor N. Mominov, the group of authors focused on didactic principles and told them:

- focusing the student's attention on the imparted knowledge in education and maintaining it until the end of the process;
- to scientifically justify any objective truth;
- to use more visual aids in teaching based on the ability and characteristics of the student;
- ensuring regularity and continuity in imparting knowledge;
- conducting the training process with practice;
- ensuring the activity and consciousness of students in the process of education and training, the principles of systematic, consistent and unity of education and training" [4]. - they emphasize.

By means of the historical method of teaching history and special methods of history education, students will have a clear and correct idea of the past, and they will acquire the

necessary practical skills. Exposing students through the auditory, visual and sensory organs helps to increase their imagination of what historical ideals did. As a result, their knowledge and skills are deepened and strengthened.

As a result of the superficial teaching of history, which often replaces vivid images of the past with dry schemes, although the students have some facts and theoretical concepts in historical issues, they do not have a correct idea of the past in whole or in part.

It is one of the urgent issues of today to convey the clear and true picture and content of history to the minds of students. Therefore, getting acquainted with the lives and activities of historical figures helps students to clearly understand historical facts, to learn about the characteristics of a certain historical period and social environment.

The components of history education that are necessary to develop acculturative skills in students include:

1. Historical consciousness and historical memory. The socio-pedagogical necessity of developing students' historical consciousness and memory can be explained as follows:

First of all, the changes taking place in the world and in our country, today's political reality and daily life needs did not reduce the public's interest in history, but on the contrary, led to a sharper perception of the past. This is a legitimate process, because the new period of change cannot be limited to a superficial study of the past. It requires a thorough understanding of all periods and processes. Because there is no future without historical memory, and the future of a nation that does not remember the past will not be bright.

Secondly, turning points in the life of nations, wars and revolutions, transition from economic growth to depression and decline, fundamental changes in the life of society have always increased interest in history. The new stage of Uzbekistan's development has put on the agenda issues related to the selection of further development paths, that is, the methods, forms, and principles of evaluating the traveled path and developing programs for the future. The answer to such questions encourages any society to re-understand the reasons that lead to the current situation in the form of each new generation.

Thirdly, today, interest in the past, seeking to find answers for the present, and choosing a path of development in order to anticipate the future are becoming common. Because understanding the past, present and future in an integral relationship allows making the right social decisions.

Fourthly, all the changes implemented in life are the result of taking into account the mentality of the people, their historical consciousness and historical memory, historical and national features, traditions and customs, their own past, all the beautiful things accumulated by the talented people of Uzbekistan during the centuries-long rich history. Therefore, as we have set ourselves the goal of building a great state, we have modern political, economic, scientific-technical, and spiritual opportunities for this, as well as a historical basis.

Fifth, being aware of the legacy of their great ancestors not only creates a sense of pride in their history in the young generation, but also the responsibility to be worthy of it and take an example from it. In Uzbekistan, young people constitute a large socio-demographic layer as the heirs of the future. the future of the country largely depends on how effectively the issues of forming the spiritual world of this young generation are solved.

2. Historical values, ideals and cultural skills. It is known that the image of every nation, regardless of its size or size, is first of all reflected in its national consciousness and psychology. National consciousness is the main form of ethnic consciousness, which is a component of social

consciousness. At the same time, it is necessary to consider that "social consciousness is the reflection of the objective world and social existence in the minds of people.

Another aspect of historical values that affects each other and the worldview is the sense of national unity, solidarity, sympathy, and cooperation. National unity, solidarity, cooperation, sympathy, harmony is to move towards certain realized common goals. On the basis of this feeling, students understand that they belong to a particular ethnic group, strive to learn more about its history and fate, show examples of self-sacrifice for the interests of the Motherland, and try to protect national interests by uniting with people belonging to their own people.

3. Careful preservation of historical, spiritual and cultural heritage. Multicultural knowledge and skills form an environment aimed at the study and understanding of historical, spiritual and cultural values, heritage, and their preservation. Careful preservation of historical, spiritual and cultural heritage is also an awareness of national duty and responsibility. An important aspect of national duty and responsibility is seen in understanding national interests. The political, economic, social relations, which have left the individual and his interests in the shadow of political beliefs, adapted to ensure the full dominance of abstract social interests, and the ideology based on this will disappear[5].

It is impossible to create the future without history, without historical memory. That is why great tasks are being assigned to historians in our society. They should restore and write the true history of our state, people, and nation. Development of historical memory is one of the laws of ethnic unification. The process of its emergence and improvement is evidence of the internal unity of the Uzbek people, their understanding of their national unity.

The systemic-functional model of development of acculturative skills in students reflected goal-oriented, theoretical-methodological, content-related, organizational and result-oriented components.

- The goal orientation of the system is determined by the achievement of certain results. Clarification of the goal is carried out by focusing on a number of questions that the developed system should answer. In order to successfully solve the problem of developing acculturative skills in students, the final result of this process should be clearly reflected. The purpose of the model was defined as the development of acculturative skills in students through the subject of "History".

- During the development of the model, it was envisaged to solve the following tasks:
 - 1) clarification of methodological approaches to the development of a model for the development of acculturative skills in students;
 - 2) clarification of the block structure of the model;
 - 3) reveal the relationship between the model block and its elements;
 - 4) to describe the block structure and elements of the model.
- The above-mentioned goals and tasks of developing acculturative skills in students are related to complex methodological approaches.

- Effective approaches to the development of acculturative skills in students can include:

- the systematic-process approach is characterized by setting a problem that reflects the logic of scientific research as the general basis of research, clarifying the main and local goals, clarifying conflicting opinions and points of view, and ensures the development of a model for the development of acculturative skills in students;

- axiological and reflexive approaches as the theoretical-methodological basis of the strategy define the directions of theoretical research, reflect its general view. These approaches make it possible to determine the value system and provide feedback in the system of developing acculturative skills in students;

- the personal-activity-oriented approach is manifested as a practical-oriented tactic aimed at determining the mechanism and procedures for organizing the activities of pedagogues and students in order to achieve the set goal, revealing the peculiarities of the practical use of the studied phenomenon.

Each methodological approach is associated with a certain system of principles that allows the realization of the set goal. The principle means requirements and basic rules for the process of development of pedagogical models, systems, etc. The principles reflect the objective requirements for the formation of the researched direction.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is necessary to take into account the opportunities of general secondary education and the professional skills of pedagogues in the development of students' acculturative skills, and their experience in conducting a pedagogical process aimed at understanding historical processes with students. It follows that the high level of pedagogic skills in general secondary education allows the use of approaches and improved methods advanced by us to achieve the intended goal.

Adabiyotlar:

1. Агибалова Е.В. Донской Г.М. Методика преподавания истории средних веков. – Москва: 1966. – Б.12.
2. Toshpolatov T., Gaffarov Ya. Methodology of teaching history. - Tashkent: University, 1999. ʘB.16.
3. Tashpolatov T., Gaffarov Ya. Methodology of teaching history. - Tashkent: University, 1999. ʘB.18.
4. Sa'diev A. Teaching the history of the peoples of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1993. - P.21.
5. Tulenov J. Spirituality and social development. - T.: Labor, 2000. - B. 15-21-
6. Sharifhojaev M. Formation of open civil society in Uzbekistan. - T.: Sharq, 2003. - 144 p.
7. Shaniozov Sh.K. The origin of the Uzbek people. - T.: Sharq, 2001. - 240 p.
8. Karimov, U. U., & Karimova, G. Y. (2021). The importance of innovative technologies in achieving educational effectiveness. Журнал естественных наук, 1(1).
9. Rayimov, A. A. (2021). Social Aspects Of The Formation Of Social Activity In Youth. Oriental Journal of Social Sciences, 1(1), 29-32.
- 10.. Tashpolatov T., Gaffarov Ya. Methodology of teaching history. - Tashkent: University, 1999.
11. Tulenov J., Jabbarov I. Development of historical consciousness is the need of the times. - T.: Labor, 2000.
12. Tulenov J. Spirituality and social development. - T.: Labor, 2000.